

The Position of Bid'at in Islam

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Bid'at in religion has caused the practice of the prophetic tradition to disappear in Islamic societies and heresies to be promoted in society instead of Islamic traditions because performing heresies instead of worship causes misguidance and depravity. Therefore, there is an urgent need to introduce Bid'at to people to get acquainted with its negative consequences. The question of the current research is what is Bid'at in religion? Is Bid'at good and bad? Who is the Bid'at initiator? And what are the negative effects of Bid'at on its initiator? The purpose of this study is to explain the concept of Bid'at in religion and its adverse effects on the Bid'at initiator. This is a qualitative literature review research based on Islamic scripts and valid scientific sources have been used. The results of this research have shown that Bid'at refers to creating a way and method worshiping in religion, similar to the way and method of Sharia to approach Almighty God. A Bid'at initiator is someone who creates something of his own in religion. There is a great deal of disagreement about whether or not to divide Bid'at into goodness and badness, and each party provided reasons to substantiate its claim, which is examined in this article and the preferred promise is specified. Creating Bid'at in religion has many negative effects on the innovator, the most important of which are mentioned in this article.

Keywords: Bid'at, innovator, religion, mundane, hereafter

Creating Bid'at in religion is a negative phenomenon that unfortunately has been prevalent among Islamic societies since ancient times and there have been people throughout history who, for various purposes, allowed themselves to Create Bid'at in religion and promote it among Islamic societies. They were Unaware that by doing so they committed a great sin and committed an act that contradicts the perfection of religion. Allah Almighty says: "Today I have perfected your faith for you" (Al-Ma'idah/3). And committing this act has adverse effects; And these unfortunate effects affect the innovator before anyone else because after the revelation of the above-blessed verse, which indicates the perfection of the holy religion of Islam, the initiation of any kind of Bid'at in the religion is considered misguidance and the perpetrator deserves worldly and hereafter punishment. Fortunately, a lot of research has been done by Islamic scholars and scientists about recognizing Bid'at in religion and its negative effects, and many books have been written, most of which are in Arabic, and where I read in Persian (Dari), research has been done so far, has not been widespread.

Problem Statement

Differences in the definition of Bid'at and its division into goodness and badness, have caused some people to Create Bid'at in religion by justifying their actions and not paying attention to the negative effects of Bid'at, so it is necessary to provide a clear definition of

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Bid'at in religion and the reasons for each. The proponents and opponents of the division of Bid'at should be discussed in a good way and the preferred promise in the field should be made clear to everyone and the effects of creating Bid'at in religion on the creator should be stated. The issue or subject of the current research is to provide a clear definition of Bid'at in religion and to express the preferred promise about dividing Bid'at into a wide range of virtues and mentioning the negative effects of Bid'at on the innovator.

The Importance of the Research

Since the existence of many Bid'at in religion has caused the practice of the tradition of the Holy Prophet of Islam to be diminished and people to be misled, therefore, there is an urgent need to fight this negative phenomenon comprehensively and to study it extensively. Research should be done so that everyone is aware of its nature, so research on Bid'at and introducing it to others, and expressing its adverse consequences on the innovator is of particular importance.

The Purpose of the Research

This is to elucidate and explain Bid'at in religion and express its negative effects on the innovator.

The Research Questions

What is Bid'at in religion?

- Is there goodness or badness in Bid'at?
- Who is an innovator?
- What are the negative effects of Bid'at on the innovator?
- What are the negative consequences of Bid'at?

Method

This is a review research paper that has been done by using Islamic scripts. A qualitative research method has been used to describe and analyze the Islamic written scripts. To obtain valid and consistent data, content analysis has been done. All the interpretations of the Holy Qur'an have been gotten from Tafseer Noor.

Definition of Bid'at

Lexical Definition of Bid'at: Bid'at means initiation and the creation of practice that did not exist before or anything that was created without a previous pattern (Afriqi, N.D: 6).

Terminological Definition of Bid'at: Bid'at in the term refers to the new tradition that was created after the completion of the religion, and in other words, Bid'at is anything that was created in the religion after the death of the Messenger of God and is contrary to the prophetic tradition (Afriqi, N.D: 6; Naqshbandi, 1385:10, Asqalani, 1379: 253).

As it is stated, there is a contradiction of opinions regarding the determination of the religious meaning of Bid'at. Some have contrasted Bid'at with Hadith, and some others have considered it to be general and inclusive of anything that has arisen since the death of the Prophet, whether it is praiseworthy or reprehensible. But the most comprehensive and preferred definition for Bid'at is: Bid'at is the initiation of a way and method in religion (for religiosity) similar to the way and method of Shari'a to approach God Almighty without any legitimate reason for its correctness Shatibi, N.D: 27).

Definition of Innovator

An innovator is a verbal noun that means initiator, and the term refers to someone who creates something of his own in religion that no one else has done before (Afriqi, N.d: 8).

Commandments on Bid'at

There is a contradiction of opinions among Islamic scholars about the ruling of Bid'at, and this contradiction is due to the division and non-division of Bid'at into various types. Az Ibn Abdul-Salam and other scholars who divided Bid'at into five types (obligatory, recommended, permissible, abominable & forbidden) say: The ruling of obligatory Bid'at is obligatory; the ruling of recommended Bid'at is recommended; the ruling of permissible Bid'at is permissible; the ruling of innovatorial Bid'at is hatred and the ruling of forbidden Bid'at is sanctity (Toyjari, 1421: 27).

Shaikh-ul-Islam Ibn Taymiyyah and other scholars who condemn all types of Bid'at say: It is prohibited to perform all types of Bid'at. Some heresies are infidelity, such as circumambulating graves to get closer to the companions of graves. And some other heresies are among the tools of polytheism, such as: making luxurious repairs on graves. And some other heresies are sin, such as the Bid'at of abandoning marriage or cutting off the sexual intercourse to get rid of lust and engage in worship for the sake of approaching God Almighty (Qahtani, N.D: 46).

The Division of Bid'at Based on Reason

Bid'at is divided into two types based on reason. A. Real Bid'at. B. Surplus Bid'at

Real Bid'at: Real Bid'at is that there is no canonical reason from Holy Qur'an, Sunnah, consensus and valid detailed or general reasoning that it is safe, and for this reason, such a thing is called Bid'at, because the innovator is approaching God Almighty by a forbidden act, such as monasticism and abandonment of marriage. The inventing an act of worship that God Almighty has not prescribed, such as adding a few prostrations to the prostrations of the prayer or performing the prayer without ablution and expressing the removal of the obligation (Almasi, N.D: 139).

Additional Bid'at: Additional Bid'at is a Bid'at that has two flaws.

First, there are reasons to prove that this is not Bid'at. Second, it has no justification and in this respect, it is similar to real Bid'at. Because this innovational act has two similarities and is not perfect in either aspect that is why it has been called additional Bid'at. Additional Bid'at concerning one of the two mentioned aspects is Sunna because it is documented by reason. And concerning the opposite aspect, it is Bid'at, because it is documented as pseudo-evidence, not reason, or it is not documented at all, and the difference between the two is that the first (ie, pseudo-reason) is a reason but is not considered a reason in terms of details and qualities.

Types of Additional Bid'at

Islamic scholars have divided Bid'at into two types.

- A Bid'at that is close to the real Bid'at, as far as it can be imagined to be real. For instance, an obliged person has two ways to worship and reach the closeness of Almighty Allah, an easy and a hard way. The obliged person chose a hard way to reach the closeness of Almighty Allah, like a person who has two baths available, hot water and cold water, but he chooses cold water. Naturally, this is against the rule of relief.
- A Bid'at that is far from real Bid'at, therefore, may be considered pure Sunnah. It is as if a person, like adhering to the Sunnah permanently or in limited times and in a limited way, is bound to the supererogatory. For instance, to hold non-Ramadan supererogatory in congregation in the Masjid. This is the beginning and the reason for its innovation is that such a thing has not been reported from the Prophet, his companions, and his righteous predecessors. Doing so causes the common people to believe that it is Sunnah, and this leads to the corruption and destruction of religion (Almasi, N.D: 141-140).

Differences of view on the division of Bid'at into goodness and badness, there have long been under the discussion among Islamic scholars which are referred to below:

The View of those who Agree with the Division of Bid'at into Goodness and Badness

Some scholars, including Imam Shafi'i, May God have mercy on him, believe that Bid'at is of two types, good Bid'at and evil Bid'at, and says: Good Bid'at agrees with the Sunnah, and evil Bid'at is that which is contrary to the Sunnah of the Messenger of God. (Naqshbandi, 2016: 49).

The reasons of those who agree with the division of Bid'at into goodness and badness:

- *Citing this Hadith in which the Prophet said:* "Whatever is good for Muslims is good for God. And whatever is bad for Muslims is bad for God" (Hakim, 1411: 83).
- *Citing this Hadith in which the Prophet said:* "Whoever innovates a good method and behavior in Islam, for him is the reward of it and the reward of the one who does it after him, without deducting anything from their rewards. And whoever innovates a bad method and behavior in Islam, it is his fault, and the sin of the one who commits it after him, without diminishing any of their sins" (Nawavi, N.D: 208).
- *The Citation and Argument are Based on the Statement of Umar Ibn al-Khattab that he said about Taraweeh Prayer:* "praying Taraweeh prayer in congregation in the mosque is a favored Bid'at". (Madani, 1406:114).
- Citing that Compiling the Holy Quran in one Mus'haf (book) and

contenting oneself with the Mus'haf of Uthman, was a good innovation in religion that companions and followers of the Prophet (PBUH) did. (Helali, N.D: 42).

- Citing that Imam Shafi'i also believed in good Bid'at. As it has been narrated from him: "There are two types of Bid'at: good Bid'at and bad Bid'at. Any Bid'at that agrees with the Sunnah is good and any Bid'at that is against the Sunnah is considered bad."
- Citing that Imam Shafi'i also believed in good Bid'at. As it has been narrated from him: "There are two types of Bid'at: good Bid'at and bad Bid'at. Any Bid'at that agrees with the Sunnah is good and any Bid'at that is against the Sunnah is considered bad." (Helali, N.D: 29).

The View of the Opponents of Dividing Bid'at into Goodness and Evil

Other Islamic scholars, including Shaykh ul-Islam Ibn Taymiyyah, May God have mercy on him, believe that the division of Bid'at into goodness and evil, is contrary to the religious documents and Hadith (Helali, N.D: 27-30).

The reasons of those who disagree with the division of Bid'at into goodness and badness:

- *Citing this Verse of Qur'an*: "Today I have perfected your faith for you, completed My favor upon you, and chosen Islam as your way." (Al-Ma'idah/3).

This blessed verse indicates that the religion of Islam is completed after the death of the Holy Prophet and there is no need to add anything to it by creating Bid'at.

- *Citing this Hadith of the Prophet in which he said*: "Every Bid'at is misguidance" (Nishapoori, N.D: 11&204). The meaning of this hadith is general and remains on its generality.
- *Citing this Hadith*: "Whoever brings into "our religion" something that is not from it, then it is rejected" (Bukhari, 1407: 63 & Nawavi, N.D: 204).

The meaning of this hadith is also general and includes any kind of Bid'at; therefore, no kind of Bid'at is good and acceptable, but all are evil and rejected. This party says in rejecting the word of those who agree with the division of Bid'at in goodness and evil: This Hadith "what Muslims think is good" is suspended in this regard. As Allama Albani said: There is no evidence that this hadith has been documented and is weak. This hadith is based on Ibn Mas'ud. Therefore, this hadith is weak and it cannot be argued against the definitive hadiths that have been included in the condemnation of Bid'at.

And the argument for this statement of Umar ibn al-Khattab: "This is the Blessing of the Bid'at" to cite and relate to the hadith "All the Bid'at is an aberration" because the legitimacy of Taraweeh prayer has been proven by the text of the hadith of the Prophet.

It is narrated from Jabir ibn Abdullah that when the Prophet (PBUH) revived one of the nights of Ramadan with the people, he prayed eight rak'ats (Taraweeh) and (after that) performed the Witr prayer.

Conclusion

By examining the issues raised in this article, it is concluded that:

- Bid'at means innovation and the creation of a new method and behavior that did not exist before or anything that was created without a previous pattern.

- The term refers to the creation of a way and method in religion (for religiosity) that is similar to the way and method of Shari'a and to approach God Almighty without any legitimate and correct reason for its correctness.
- Az Ibn Abdul-Salam and other scholars who divided Bid'at into five types (obligatory, recommended, permissible, abominable and forbidden) say: The ruling of obligatory Bid'at is obligatory; the ruling of recommended Bid'at is recommended; the ruling of permissible Bid'at is permissible; the ruling of innovational Bid'at is hatred and the ruling of forbidden Bid'at is sanctity.
- The division of Bid'at into good and evil is a division that has no strong reason. And it is in conflict with the explicit text of the Holy Quran and the authentic prophetic hadiths, and those who believe in dividing Bid'at into goodness and evil have not provided acceptable reasons, but all their reasons have been criticized.
- The preferred promise about Bid'at is the promise of those who believe that Bid'at should not be divided into goodness and evil. They don't allow Muslims to Create in terms of Islamic structure and worshiping methods and behaviors.

Suggestions

- My first suggestion is for the holy scholars to explain the Bid'at and the consequences of Bid'at in religion to the general public by quoting the verses of the Holy Quran and the prophetic hadiths through scientific methods and by writing authoritative books.
- The second suggestion is for the students of Islamic sciences to make more efforts to be aware of Bid'at and the consequences of Bid'at in religion; And to seriously fight against Bid'at and innovators; because the more they stay away from Bid'at and superstition, the more they will follow the correct prophetic Sunnah.
- My third suggestion is for the general Muslims to listen to the words of the divine scholars to preserve their religion and stay safe from the evil consequences of Bid'at, and to oppose Bid'at to the best of their ability, and to advise their subordinates as well.

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